

On the Constitution of Arsenious Sulphide Sol in Presence or Absence of Arsenious Acid.

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In a recent paper (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 2, 301) Mukherjee and Chaudhury have shown that, in the presence of acids, variations in the migration velocity of the colloidal particles of arsenious sulphide prepared under different conditions are different. Freundlich and Nathansohn (*Koll. Zeit.*, 1921, 28, 258) have suggested that the free hydrogen sulphide present in arsenious sulphide sols is photochemically oxidised to sulphur dioxide which again reacts with hydrogen sulphide to form pentathionic acid and sulphur. The sulphur adsorbs polythionate ions and thus passes into the colloidal sulphur. Murphy and Mathews (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, 45, 16) mention that the assumption of the presence of polythionic acids is necessary to explain the increase in the conductivity of the sols on exposure to light. Bhatnagar and Lakshan Rao have also shown in an interesting study (*Kol.-Zeit.*, 1923, 33, 164) that the transformation of the colour of orange sols of arsenious sulphide into yellow is due to the oxidation of the particles. Accordingly it seemed desirable to investigate the constitution of different samples of arsenious sulphide sols, as prepared and used in this laboratory.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Arsenious sulphide sols were prepared under two conditions:

(1) Equal volumes of a solution of arsenious acid prepared by diluting a saturated solution with equal volume of conductivity water, and of a saturated solution of hydrogen sulphide in conductivity water, were mixed quickly and thoroughly shaken (Sol A). That the sol A contains free arsenious acid was shown by passing hydrogen sulphide into the liquid filtered from arsenious sulphide sol after precipitation by an electrolyte.

(2) Equal volumes of a solution of arsenious acid obtained by diluting a saturated solution with equal volume of conductivity water, and of a saturated solution of hydrogen sulphide in conductivity, water were mixed quickly and thoroughly shaken. Hydrogen sulphide was then passed into the mixture till no free arsenious acid could be detected in the filtrate after precipitation by an electrolyte. Pure hydrogen was then bubbled through the colloidal solution till there was no free hydrogen sulphide (Sol B).

Portions of these sols were taken for determination of arsenic and sulphur. Twenty-five c.c. of the sol were dissolved in excess of liq. ammonia fort, oxidised by hydrogen peroxide, evaporated to dryness in a water-bath and dissolved in water. The solution containing arsenate and sulphate was filtered from impurities present in the ammonia. The precipitate was washed carefully and the wash-liquor was added to the previous filtrate. Arsenic was then estimated as magnesium pyroarsenate, and sulphur as barium sulphate. The arsenic present as sulphide in a colloidal state in sol A was found from the difference in the total arsenic and that present in the filtrate after precipitation with an electrolyte. The

arsenic not present in the colloidal state was estimated as above in same volume of the sol after removing the colloid by coagulating it. Results are given below :

In column II are given the number of gram atoms of arsenic present as colloidal sulphide in 25 c.c. sol. In column III are given the number of gram atoms of sulphur which have combined with the number of atoms of arsenic given in column II to form the sulphide. The ratio between them is given in column IV.

I	II	III	IV.
Sol. A.	0.0007975	0.001163	1: 1.46
Sol. B.	0.001213	0.002416	1: 2

Discussion.

The constitution of sol A, where arsenious acid was in excess, corresponds to orpiment, arsenic trisulphide. The constitution of sol B, where arsenious acid as well as hydrogen sulphide was absent, corresponds either to As_2S_3 , As_2S_5 or to As_2S_3 , H_2S . The latter formula As_2S_3 , H_2S is the more probable one because very little or none of the pentasulphide is formed in the absence of any acid. Bhatnagar and Lakshan Rao (*loc. cit.*) have analysed the coagulum of arsenious sulphide sols prepared in a manner similar to sol B but in the dark and have found it to be of the composition As_2S_{2x} , xH_2S .

They have also suggested that arsenious trisulphide found on exposure to light in the coagulum is formed by the oxidation of As_2S_{2x} , H_2S as represented below :

The possibility of such a reaction in the present case seems to be remote. Our results show that in diffused light As_2S_3 , H_2S is formed when prepared in presence of excess of hydrogen sulphide. This substance gives out

free hydrogen sulphide, and the oxidation referred to by previous authors is of the hydrogen sulphide thus generated. The ratio of arsenic to sulphur in the sols has been determined twice with identical results.

The composition As_2S^3 , H_2S corresponds to a definite acid, meta-thioarsenious acid. Our results suggest that colloidal particles of arsenious sulphide when prepared in the presence of excess of hydrogen sulphide have the composition As_2S_3 , H_2S whereas, when arsenious oxide is in excess, the simple trisulphide is formed.

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